

CROSS-LINGUISTIC CHALLENGES IN TRANSLATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Phraseological units – such as idioms, collocations, set similes and multi-word expressions – pose significant challenges in translation and interpreting due to their culturally bound meanings and structural specificity. This presentation explores the cross-linguistic difficulties involved in rendering such expressions across Russian, Romanian, English, and German. By analyzing idiomatic structures and strategies for equivalence, the study highlights how cultural context, syntactic flexibility, and metaphorical meaning influence translation choices. The research draws on examples from literary, journalistic, and spoken discourse, aiming to identify patterns, pitfalls, and effective solutions for maintaining both meaning and stylistic nuance in multilingual contexts.